

Anionic Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II)

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Gillespie and Nyholm¹ have listed, on the basis of ligand field theory, the stereochemistry for complexes of the transition metals. It is well known that stereochemistry of complex molecules depend very much on the configuration of the non-bonding shell. Since d^0 , d^5 and d^{10} configurations represent spherically symmetrical non-bonding shells being empty, half-full and full respectively, these are expected to cause the least perturbation to the preferred stereochemistry. Divalent cadmium ion has a completely filled d^{10} electronic structure and forms stable tetrahedral complexes using the sp^3 hybrid orbitals. Many such complexes are reported² in the literature. Several complexes have been isolated with ligands containing nitrogen donor atoms³⁻⁵, where the structure is presumably tetrahedral. Cadmium also forms complexes of the type $M_6[CdX_4]$, where $M = Et_4N^+$, Me_4N^+ , Ph_4P^+ or Ph_4As^+ , similar to the corresponding complexes of zinc and mercury.

The compounds reported in this communication are examples of tetrahedral compounds of cadmium, containing the heterocyclic aromatic amines, 3-methyl pyridine or *p*-anisidine and the quaternary ammonium salt tetraethyl ammonium bromide, as the ligands. The compounds have the general formulae $[Et_4N][CdBr_3]$, where $L = 3\text{-methyl pyridine}$ or *p*-anisidine.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Complexes : All compounds were prepared from A.R. grade chemicals. The purity of the samples were established by estimating the metal as $CdNH_4PO_4 \cdot H_2O$ and the halogen as AgBr.

Tetraethyl ammonium (3-methyl pyridine) tri-bromo Cadmium (II) : A hot solution of tetraethyl ammonium bromide (0.52 gm) in absolute alcohol and 3-methylpyridine (0.23 ml.) were thoroughly mixed and added to a hot solution of cadmium bromide tetrahydrate (0.86 gm.) in absolute alcohol. On shaking and cooling a white crystalline compound separated out almost immediately, and this was suction filtered, washed with ethanol, then with ether and finally dried *in vacuo*. The compound did not melt or decompose upto 250°. *Anal* : Calcd. for $[(C_2H_5)_4N][Cd(3\text{-Mepy})Br_3]$, Cd-18.5%, Br-41.6%, found Cd-19.2%, Br-41.8%.

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Tetraethyl ammonium (p-anisidine) tri-bromo Cadmium (II): Prepared as above using tetraethyl ammonium bromide (0.52 gm), *p*-anisidine (0.3 gm) and $\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.86 gm), when a crystalline light-grey coloured compound separated out, which was suction filtered, washed with ethanol, then with ether and dried in *vacuo*. The compound did not melt or decompose upto 250°. *Anal*: Calcd. for $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}][\text{Cd}(p\text{-anisidine})\text{Br}_3]$, Cd-18.5%, Br-39.6%, found Cd-18.3%, Br-39.7%.

Physical Measurements: The conductance measurements were carried out using a Phillips conductivity bridge type PR9500 and a dip type cell previously calibrated with aqueous KCl solution. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens at room temperature using Gouy method, the apparatus being calibrated with $\text{HgCo}(\text{CNS})_4$.⁷ The compounds were diamagnetic. The infra-red absorption spectra of the compounds were recorded as Nujol mulls in the region 4,000–650 cm^{-1} using Perkin-Elmer 337 recording spectrophotometer with rock-salt optics using a polystyrene strip for calibration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The compounds are 1 : 1 electrolytes in acetone and water medium, as evident from their observed Λ_m values, and are diamagnetic. In each case, the comparison of the infra-red spectra between the free ligand and the metal complexes were made and this indicates the coordination of the amine and the tetraethyl-ammonium bromide to the central cadmium atom, since most of the ligand absorption bands are either split or shifted to a higher frequency region⁸. All these results indicate a tetrahedral structure for the cadmium (II) ion in these complexes, involving the use of $5s5p^3$ orbitals for bonding. These complexes are examples of anionic mixed ligand complexes of cadmium (II) containing both the nitrogen and the bromine as the donor atoms. Investigations in this field are in progress as a result of our interest in the study of post-transition elements and detailed results will be published in a future communication.

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